

From individual to joint species distribution models: a comparison of model complexity and predictive performance

May 28, 2019

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Journal of Biogeography - SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Geographic Distribution of the Quality of Fit by Taxon in the Hierarchical Multi-Species Model

The following plots show the geographic distribution of the probabilities of occurrence and observations for all taxa in the hierarchical multi-species model UF0 when calibrated to the whole BDM dataset. Regions with large blue points or small red points indicate a good quality of fit. The probability of occurrence increases with point size and the point fill corresponds to the probability of occurrence at the 5th (filled) and 95th (unfilled) quantiles of the marginal posterior distributions of the probabilities of occurrence; large differences in the point sizes at a sample location indicate a high uncertainty in the calibrated probability of occurrence. Taxa are ordered by decreasing number of occurrences.

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Chironomidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Limoniidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 2

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Simuliidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Oligochaeta*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 4

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_alpinus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 5

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Empididae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 6

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_rhodani*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 7

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ceratopogonidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 8

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Psychodidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 9

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Elmidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 10

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Isoperla*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 11

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Planariidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 12

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_muticus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 13

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Gammaridae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 14

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Athericidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 15

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Prostigmata

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 16

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_tristis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 17

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hydraenidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 18

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_lateralis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 19

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_mortoni*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 20

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Nematoda

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 21

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Sericostoma*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 22

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Scirtidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 23

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Habroleptoides_confusa*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 24

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Blephariceridae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 25

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_helveticus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 26

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Brachyptera_risi*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 27

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Sphaeriidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 28

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dixidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 29

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Amphinemura*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 30

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Odontocercum_albicorne*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dictyogenus

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 32

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Tinodes

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 33

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Tipulidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 34

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Plectrocnemia

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 35

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_minima*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 36

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus discolor*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 37

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_loyolaea*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 38

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Epeorus_alpicola*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 39

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_braueri*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 40

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Epeorus_assimilis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 41

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Stratiomyidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 42

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Philopotamus_ludificatus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 43

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Habrophlebia_lauta*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 44

Probability of occurrence vs observations of DugesIIDae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 45

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Centroptilum_luteolum*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 46

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_venosus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 47

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_puthzi*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 48

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Chloroperla_susemicheli*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 49

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Paraleptophlebia_submarginata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 50

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_picteti*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 51

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_lutheri*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 52

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dytiscidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 53

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Thaumaleidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 54

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_hirticornis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 55

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_alpestris*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 56

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Capnioneura_nemuroides*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 57

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_brevistyla*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 58

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ephemera_danica*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 59

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_picteti*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 60

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Habroleptoides_auberti*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 61

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Metanoea*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 62

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Siphonoperla_torrentium*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 63

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Glossosoma*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 64

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_nigra*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 65

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Lymnaeidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 66

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_siltalai*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 67

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Electrogena_ujhelyii*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 68

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhabdiopteryx*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 69

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Perloides

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 70

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Erpobdellidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 71

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_intricata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 72

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Perla_grandis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 73

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Wormaldia*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 74

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Asellidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 75

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Cryptothrix_nebulicola*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 76

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_nimborum*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 77

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Sialidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 78

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ptychopteridae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 79

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hydrophilidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 80

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_alpinus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 81

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Glossiphoniidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 82

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus annulatus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 83

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Cordulegastriidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 84

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Siphonoperla_montana*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 85

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ephemerella_mucronata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 86

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Serratella ignita*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 87

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_hybrida*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 88

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_nivata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 89

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Anthomyiidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 90

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_major*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 91

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Lype

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 92

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hydroptilidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 93

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus_biguttatus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 94

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_torrentis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 95

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_degrangei*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 96

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Perla_marginata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 97

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemurella_pictetii*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 98

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ancyclus

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 99

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Tabanidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 100

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Polycentropus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 101

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Potamophylax_cingulatus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 102

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus_melanchaetes*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 103

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_semicolorata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 104

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_dorieri*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 105

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hydrobiidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 106

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Goeridae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 107

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Gyrinidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 108

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Calopterygidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 109

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dinocras

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 110

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Lepidostomatidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 111

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Brachyptera_seticornis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 112

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_gratianopolitana*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 113

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_grischuna*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 114

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecclisopteryx_madida*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 115

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Rhagionidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 116

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Physidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 117

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_praemorsa*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 118

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Melampophylax_mucoreus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 119

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_vernus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 120

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Niphargidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 121

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Chloroperla_tripunctata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 122

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_marginata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 123

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Agapetus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 124

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Torleya_major*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 125

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus nigrescens*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 126

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_intermedia*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 127

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_flexuosa*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 128

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus_muelleri*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 129

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_tenuis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 130

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Electrogena_lateralis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 131

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Capnia*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 132

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Haliplidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 133

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dolichopodidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 134

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Micrasema_morosum*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 135

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Psychomyia_pusilla*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 136

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Caenis_macrura*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 137

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_instabilis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 138

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Syrphidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 139

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Siphonurus lacustris*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 140

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_stigmatica*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 141

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_praecox*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 142

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Corixidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 143

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Planorbidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 144

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_schmiedi*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 145

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_vardarensis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 146

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_bucерatus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 147

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Scathophagidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 148

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_pubescens*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 149

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Allogamus_auricollis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 150

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_torrentium*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 151

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Mystacides*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 152

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Coenagrionidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 153

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dryopidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 154

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Synagapetus_dubitans*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 155

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_rosinae*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 156

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Catagapetus_nigrans*
mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 157

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Astacidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 158

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Osmylidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 159

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Piscicolidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 160

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dendrocoelidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 161

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_melanonyx*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 162

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Glyphotaelius_pellucidus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 163

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Psephenidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 164

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Gerridae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 165

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_meyeri*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 166

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_landai*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 167

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Philopotamus_variegatus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 168

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Synagapetus_iridipennis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 169

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Halesus_radiatus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 170

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_fasciata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 171

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus monticola*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 172

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Lepidoptera

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 173

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Veliidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 174

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus_alpinus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 175

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ernodes

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 176

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Platycnemididae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 177

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Cnidaria

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 178

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Athripsodes

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 179

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Caenis_rivulorum*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 180

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Anabolia

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 181

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_inermis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 182

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_allobrogica*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 183

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ptilocolepus_granulatus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 184

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Cloeon_dipterum*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 185

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Baetis_nexus

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 186

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Caenis_horaria*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 187

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_dinarica*
mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 188

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_nimborella*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 189

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Bithyniidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 190

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Valvatidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 191

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Aphelocheiridae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 192

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Chaetopteryx_major*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 193

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecclisopteryx_guttulata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 194

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_niger*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 195

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_hippopus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 196

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_cambrica*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 197

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Mesoveliidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 198

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Holocentropus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 199

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Besdolus_imhoffi*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 200

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_auberti*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 201

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_simulatrix*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 202

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_saxonica*
mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 203

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_dorsalis*
mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 204

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Diplectrona atra*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 205

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Chaoboridae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 206

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Consortophylax consors*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 207

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Habrophlebia_eldae*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 208

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Limnephilus lunatus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 209

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Notidobia_ciliaris*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 210

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_liebenauae*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 211

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Gomphidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 212

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_nubecularis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 213

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Oecetis_testacea*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 214

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Caenis_luctuosa*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 215

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hymenoptera

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 216

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Beraea_pullata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 217

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Micrasema_setiferum*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 218

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Cheumatopsyche_lepida*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 219

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ceraclea_annulicornis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 220

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_cinerea*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 221

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus mixtus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 222

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Agrypnia

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 223

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Habrophlebia_fusca*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 224

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_pellucidula*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 225

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Sciomyzidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 226

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ephydriidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 227

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Halesus_rubricollis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 228

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_rauscheri*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 229

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Beraea_maurus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 230

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Curculionidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 231

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Notonectidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 232

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_glareosa*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 233

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_pseudosignifera*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 234

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Potamanthus_luteus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 235

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Heptagenia_sulphurea*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 236

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Micropterna_nycterobia*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 237

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ceraclea_dissimilis*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 238

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Chrysomelidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 239

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_carpatoalpina*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 240

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_armata*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 241

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Culicidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 242

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus_chrysotus*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 243

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_rectispina*

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 244

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Acroloxiidae

mSDM UF0: Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 245

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Posterior

- 5th quantile
- 95th quantile

Observation

- Absence
- Presence